

AN EFFICIENT ALTERNATE METHOD TO IMPROVE NETWORK TRANSMISSION DURING NETWORK FAILURES

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ABSTRACT:

External Flow is our proposed work which aims at separate the controller software from the forwarding hardware of a router or switch. The External Flow work is based on the approach that the forwarding information data (FID) of a switch can be programmed via a controller which resides at a separate hardware. The goal of this work is create a standard pen management interface to the forwarding hardware of a router or switch. The aim of this work is DPARC “External ARchitecture Carrier grade networks” is to implement External Flow in carrier grade networks. Reliability is a major issue to deploy External Flow in these networks. This work proposes the addition of a fast restoration mechanism in External Flow and evaluates the performance by comparing the switchover time and packet loss to existing restoration options in a current External Flow implementation.

KEY WORDS: External Flow, Restore, Protect, Carrier Grade Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

The aim of the External Flow architecture [1] is to provide a standard open management interface to the forwarding hardware of a router or switch, i.e to test an experimental protocol in the network that used in every day. This protocol is based on the issue, that most if the modern routers/switches contain FID (Forwarding Information Data) and FID is implemented by using Content Addressable Memory. The External Flow provides a protocol to program this FID via “include/discard” entries in a Flowing Table. The Flowing Table is an abstraction of a FID. In External Flow , all the logic is performed on a central system, called the External Flow controller which manages the External Flow switches using the External Flow protocol as shown in (Fig. 1). The External Flow switch consists of a Flowing Table; which performs packet lookup (read the header part of packet) and forward, and a secure channel to an external controller.

A Flowing Entry in the Flowing Table consists data about packet as described, (a) a “header of packet ” which routes the flow, (b) “functionality” which states, the method to process the packet, and (c) “history” which records the number of packets; bytes for data at each flowing ; and the time since the last packet has been matched up per flow. The external controller deploys these Flow Entries in Flowing Tables of External Flow switches. All the incoming packets processed by the External Flow switches are compared every time data in the Flowing able. If, is there any match Flowing Entry, the required functionalities for that entry is done on that packet. Otherwise, the received packet is directly forwarded to the external controller on the secure channel. The external controller

is now performs the functionalities i.e it identifies how the packet should be routed or handled, either by including no Flowing Entries or by including valid Flow Entries in the External Flow switches.

Figure 1: External Flow

The protected channel between the External Flow switch and External controller is the one of network layers, i.e transport layer protected channel. And the packets between External Flow switches and External controller has External Flow header above transport layer header.

The External Flow switch is adopted by the software switch i.e vSwitch (<http://openvswitch.org/>) implementation. And our work proposed vSwitch for our emulation as it is a production quality, multi-layer virtual switch which is designed to enable massive network automation.

Many attempts has been already been carried out to make an External Flow controller. These are NOX [2], Beacon [3], Onix [4], Helios [5] and Maestro [6]. This work uses the NOX as an External Flow controller. This is because it is Open-Source, widely used and provides a simplified platform for writing network control software in C++ or Python.

DPARC (Divide ARchitecture Carrier grade networks) [7] is the work, which is aimed for inventing and implementation of a new Divide in the architecture of the future internet and its building blocks. DPARC is the implementation of scalable carrier class functionalities based on the External Flow concepts. And our aim of the DPARC is to implement the External Flow in carrier grade networks. The term "carrier grade" [8] describes a set of operations and requirements the architecture which should support in order to provide the operational part of network operators.

The requirements are (a) Scalability (2) Reliability (3) Quality of Service (QoS) and (4) Service Management. Carrier grade networks should be able to detect and recover from incidents without impacting users. Hence a requirement is added in the carrier grade network so that it should recover from failure within 50 ms sub interval [9]. Keeping this requirement in mind, this work is carried out to enable fast recovery in External Flow networks.

The mechanisms [10] to be used in carrier grade networks to handle recovery can be divided into Restoration and protection. In case of protection, all the paths are pre calculated and reserved before an interruption or failure occurs. If a failure occurs, no additional work is needed to establish the secured path. Anyhow, in the case of restore, the recovery paths can be either pre computed or dynamically computed and allocated, but resources are not reserved until failure occurs. Thus, when a failure occurs additional signaling is needed to establish the restoration path. Protection is a proactive strategy while restoration is a reactive strategy.

The work which we had proposed, we compare all the restoration options available in External Flow networks. And, the work which we had proposed, we add quick

restoration mechanism for External Flow networks and examine its performance by comparing the switchover times and packet loss to the existing restoration options in a current External Flow implementation.

II. EXISTING METHODS TO HANDLE FAILURE IN OPENFLOW NETWORKS

The External Flow protocol [11] derives the control messages which are exchanged between External Flow switches and External controller. For this work, there are two messages, they are, (a) "packet in" and (b) "packet out". The packet, which is received by the data path and needs to send this to the controller, it will be sent via "packet in" messages. Similarly, when External controller needs to send the packet out through data path of External Flow switch, it sends a "packet out" message.

A) External Flow Mechanisms for handling failures

External Flow adapts an on-demand approach. Flowing Entries are not added proactively in switches. If a data packet arrives at an External Flow switch and if it does not match any Flowing Entry, then it requests the Flowing Entry from the external controller by sending "packet in" message. Suppose, if the Flowing Entry is present then External Flow switches, then the packet is directly forward the data packet according to the Flowing Entry, without contacting the external controller.

The failure can be eliminated when a new packet is arrived and the new correct Flowing Entry is added in External Flow switches after the failure occurs. We can also assume that, the recovery from the failure depends on the time when the External Flow switch again requests the Flowing Entry from the External controller. With the above discussion we can assume that, the recovery from failure always depends on the life of flow in gentries in Flowing Table.

The life-period of Flowing Entries are associated with two intervals they are "idle-period timeout" and "hard-period timeout" [12]. Idle-period timeout illustrates the time when the Flow Entries should be removed due to lack of activity. It is the time interval of a Flowing Entry with which the External Flow switch has not received the packet of a particular flow of that entry. Hard-period timeout illustrates the maximum life of Flow Entries, regardless of activity. External Flow switches remove their Flowing Entries from the Flowing Tables after the expiration of one or both the intervals. As the longer value of these intervals, the longer interval time of the External Flow switches will take to recover from failure. The smaller the value, as more as packets will be forwarded to the controller to refresh the Flowing Entries.

III. CYCLE / LOOP FREE METHOD AT EXTERNALFLOW ENVIRONMENT

Restoration method requires duplicate paths in External Flow Switch topology. External controller method may need flooding of data packets when destination is unknown. In addition to that, ARP requests with broadcast address are always flooded in network. That is why , restoration requires any one of the minimum spanning tree protocol (MSTP) [13] or any other loop free technology at External Flow switch to run restoration experiment in External Flow Networks. External Flow refers the software [12], IEEE 802.1D in its networks. To enable IEEE 802.11, switch should first support IEEE 802.1D protocol. Now to use IEEE 802.1D of a switch, External Flow software should be enabled with _stp option. Those switches that do support it are expected process all 802.1D packets locally before performing flowing loop up. If the MSTP or any other loop free technology is not available, then, flooded packets travel in a loop. The very first packet which was flooded may persist indefinitely in the network cycle causing congestion. Second drawback is, method for finding destination path by flooding may not function correctly because a switch may receive packets from a source via multiple ports.

- *if(Flowing Entries included in ExternalFlow (EF) switches with respect to S*
- *Discard the Flowing Entries from each EF whose entry is wrong due to affected path S*
- *Re link path S1 in EF Switches by including Flowing Entries in each ExternalFlow switch.*

Figure 2: External Flow Network Architecture

IV. QUICK RECOVERY FOR EXTERNALFLOW NETWORKS

Quick Recovery in an External Flow network needs a quick action of the external controller on a link change event. The algorithm for quick recovery is explained below. Quick recovery is possible only, if the wrong Flowing Entries are discarded from all the External Flow switches and new entries are installed quickly after detecting the link failure in the existing path.

Table 1: Expected Time analysis for Link Events

It is possible with the help of External controller only if

- *The External controller knows the status about the failure*
- *The External controller reveals the previous path which was established by adding Flowing Entries in External Flow switches*
- *The External controller is able to manipulate a new path to replace the older path*
- *The External controller should have the current flowing in the network.*

Paths	Two Path	Path: <AFE>	Two Path	Path: <ACDE>	Two Path	Path: <AFE>
Link 1	Up		Down	Up		
Link 2	Up	Down		Up		Down
Link 5	Down					
Events			1 st		2 nd	
Data Traffic	Ping Started at the interval of 10 ms					
Time Scale	1 s	30 s	Time Varied	5 s	240 s	5 s 240 s

ALGORITHM

- *Initial: Link Change Event on External Controller*
- *For every calculated path (S) through External Controller*
- *if(Path S affected by link change)*
- *Recalculate the new available path (S1)*

V. CONCLUSION

External Flow architecture allows us to implement restoration options in External Flow networks which are much quicker than MAC re convergence Or the client-initiated recovery using a new ARP request. Our fast recovery method can be cope up in any method where controller is able to detect the failure by some means. In our fast restoration mechanism, flow is able to switch to another path within 12 ms interval regardless of the time left to expire timeouts of the Flowing Entries.

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